

PHILOLOGY

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF STUDENTS' ORAL SPEECH DEVELOPMENT

Alaviyya N.

*Teacher of the "English Language and Methodology" department of the Faculty of Foreign Languages,
Nakhcivan State University in Azerbaijan*

Abstract

The increasing demand for the English language in modern times, its being a common means of communication between different language speakers, requires the formation of oral speech in this language. However, a number of problems and difficulties are encountered during the formation of oral speech in language learners who are not native speakers. Therefore, this article discusses the actual problems of the development of students' oral language skills.

Keywords: the English language, students, oral speech, communicative language learning, problems and difficulties.

To learn English is to use foreign language tools during conversation with other people. As a result, speech in a foreign language is formed. Speech in a foreign language differs due to its rather complex psychological structure, it is divided into different types of processes and varies depending on how the tools of the foreign language are actually used. Since learning a foreign language has practical goals, if practical language learning is a speech activity, it should be clear to every teacher that foreign language learners should be taught speech activities in a foreign language. However, in order to successfully move forward in this direction, it is important to know the basic psychological characteristics and regularities of human speech. Human communication through language is manifested in two forms: oral and written speech.

Like written speech, oral speech can be both passive and active speech activity. The actual act of human speech communication requires a speaker (or writer) on the one hand, and a listener (or reader) on the other. If the first creates his active written or oral speech, then expresses this or that personal opinion, the second receives this speech passively by reading or listening.

There are mainly four processes in speech activity: listening and speaking - in oral speech; reading and writing - in written speech. Some methodists, referring to the practical acquisition of a foreign language, note that those who learn a foreign language should be able to not only listen, read, speak and write in the language they learn, but even translate from one language to another. To this end, they add several different translation processes to the four basic processes of speech - oral or written translation from mother tongue to a foreign language or from a foreign language to mother tongue, as well as reading aloud and writing a speech. However, we cannot agree with this, because translation is not a speech activity, but a mental activity [3, p.68].

In speech activity, different means of language are not always expressed in the same way. When listening and speaking, people receive ready-made speech products created by other people. This type of language acquisition is usually called receptive. When a person speaks and writes, he constructs a certain oral speech and reproduces it in his memory. At this time, his speech becomes reproductive.

Sometimes developing speech acts is related to one's imagination. So, when performing speech acts, a person always has an idea about his goal. V.A. Benediktov interpreted the main goal of the mentioned theory and applied the successful term "imagined situation". A movement task is presented to the moving person as a model of the next movement. When I'm about to say "Pass me the salt, please", we don't imagine the salt, only our action with the salt - that is, how we use it. Or when we look for a key, we imagine the work process we will do with this key, not the key. [1, p.130]

Speech activity is a means of communication that is generally involved in the concept of oral speech. Speech activity, from this point of view, has a dual nature, it involves the speaker on the one hand, and the hearer on the other. By performing the act of oral speech, the speaker transmits some information to the listener. The listener receives the content of the spoken speech. The act of communication can be considered complete if the communication between the hearer and the speaker is closed. During speaking and hearing, we witness the realization of the psychological mechanisms of speech.

For this, we need to clearly define the formal and content plan of speech communication. It is necessary to refer to the formal plan such language material from which it is possible to make speech operations and speech acts. The content plan should include the expressed speech acts and the content of the oral act corresponding to the specific situation should be added. There is no doubt that the purpose of the act of communication is to give and receive the content of the speech act. Here the question arises: what are the conditions of speech communication - if a known goal can be achieved, then an effective goal can be achieved almost without thinking, if the content of the speech act has fallen into a clear point of consciousness, and the language material is this express the content and let it stay out of consciousness. It should be noted that the work of speech during communication is as follows: although the carrier of the content is concrete language material, speech acts are built from it, the consciousness of the speaker and the listener is focused on the content of the speech act. If we consider the mechanism of speech activity, it is not difficult to explain what is

being said; speech acts, its connection to the act of behavior occurs without the participation of consciousness based on the construction. Here the two-way specific feature of speech communication manifests itself. The formal plan of the speech is implemented in unobstructed speech communication when the speech act serving a specific situation is marked in identical speech operations in both the hearer and the speaker in their speech experience.

According to research, English language learners face problems in both speaking and writing. For instance, learners of foreign language who are studying to become fluent in the target language may have several challenges, including internalizing and externalizing challenges. Cognitive features (e.g. intelligence); internal challenges; language ability; and language learning strategies and influential factors (e.g. anxiety, motivation, risk-taking); being ready to communicate; implies factors such as language relation. However, external challenges relate to first language, social class, teachers, and second language curriculum. Numerous studies have discussed the challenges faced by foreign language students, but some of these studies have been done to address these challenges. However, in order to handle these challenges, using communicative strategies ought to improve strategic skills of foreign language learners, since they can help learners to handle the communication difficulties they encounter while speaking, and they can cause better acquiring.

Communication strategies are used by learners to solve communication difficulties and failures according to the lack of ready linguistic sources. Sometimes learners cannot carry out messages or conversations as accurately as they would in their native language, make use of communicative strategies to deliver these messages, or communicate uninterruptedly. Linguists determine communicative strategy in various methods in accordance with their various perspectives. For instance, C.Færch and G.Kasper accept communication strategies from a psychological approach [2, p.20]. E. Tarone examines communication strategies from an interactive point of view, while D. Brown looks at communication strategies from the point of view of error sources.

Some of the problems faced by English language learners include:

Initially, pronunciation difficulties are connected to accent, others are connected to intonation. Following, one of the other important issues connected to the difficulties faced by adult learners in Azerbaijan is the excessive use of the Azerbaijani language in and out of the classroom. However because it is easier to use, language learners use their native language in the classroom. Thus, many language learners are not disciplined in communicating in a foreign language in the classroom. Studies show that the use of the local language is an inevitable phenomenon. The use of native languages by teachers and students turned out to be systematic. J. Harmer states that if learners are required to discuss a certain subject and they cannot express their thoughts, they switch to their native language [4, p.394].

Thirdly, another obvious difficulty is anxiety. Language anxiety can affect the communication tactics learners use in classroom. As a result, this can hinder students' language acquisition. For instance, a nervous-

ness learner may escape taking part in classroom discussions and may decrease his or her performance in social communication. Speaking or performing something making use of a target language in a class setting can cause learners nervousness since they must make unknown voices in front of an audience, or instructors can ask some questions that learners have to answer. Additionally, Horvitz proposed three kinds of language performance anxiety: communication anxiety, social evaluation, and test anxiety, which refer to the fright or trouble of learners of negative assessment. In addition, D. J. Young classified resources of troublesness into various kinds, as interpersonal and personal, student-teacher mutual relation, instructors' beliefs about language learning, learners' beliefs about language learning, classroom and test activities [5, p.426].

Fourth, the challenges encountered by Azerbaijani learners include to make use of adjectives; excessive use of syntactic and grammatical rules; idioms and prepositions; related to articulation, negative change and semantic mistakes.

Eventually, learners find occasionally it hard to communicate fluently in the foreign language when being engaged in academic subjects or general everyday subjects. For example, when we have a concrete debate, learners cannot go on their speech.

In addition, there are other reasons: excessive use of the native language, but the reasons for using the mother tongue in the classroom are that language learners are shy, do not have sufficient language skills, or are reluctant to communicate in a second language. Additionally, the majority of these difficulties are able to be attributed to the distinctions in the intonation of Azerbaijani and English languages. Moreover, inadequate vocabulary, absence of essential vocabulary to convey the meaning. For that reason, they are not able to maintain the interaction for a long time is also one of the reasons. Limited vocabulary often leads to communication problems. Not finding the right words to express thoughts while communication may cause to self-consciousness or removal from the conversation. Finally, absence of relevant knowledge of learners entering the university. For example, in research, when several university English freshmen were asked to pronounce a series of simple words, they mispronounced these words and attributed this to their previous teachers mispronouncing some of the words.

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